

Protocol:

Outcomes in Critically Ill Adults with Hypoxemic Respiratory Failure and New-Onset Atrial Fibrillation in the ICU: A Substudy of the HOT-ICU and HOT-COVID Trials

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1. Background

New-onset atrial fibrillation (NOAF) is a common arrhythmia in adult patients admitted to the intensive care unit (ICU) and is associated with prolonged hospitalisation and increased morbidity and mortality (1, 2). Intravenous administration of amiodarone is recommended as the drug of choice to treat NOAF in ICU patients followed by digoxin and beta-blockers (3, 4).

Amiodarone, a class III antiarrhythmic agent, is used for both acute and long-term treatment of atrial fibrillation (AF). It is well known that prolonged use of amiodarone can lead to significant toxicity and adverse effects (5-7). Among these, amiodarone-induced pulmonary toxicity (APT) is one of the most severe adverse effects and may be fatal (6). Acute APT after short-term treatment with amiodarone in the ICU has recently been described in a systematic review showing that the evidence for this is based on case series and case reports only (8). The clinical diagnosis of acute APT in adult ICU patients is challenging due to co-existing severe illnesses, particularly acute respiratory failure, and lack of specific diagnostic tests (9). Some authors recommend that amiodarone should be used with caution in ICU patients until solid evidence is available (10). The adverse effects of digoxin and beta-blockers are less severe and terminates when the dose is reduced, or the drug is discontinued.

The aim of the present study is to evaluate the impact of NOAF on mortality, days alive without life support and days alive out of hospital at 90 days follow-up in ICU patients with hypoxaemic respiratory failure, by comparing patients with NOAF to patients with no NOAF during their ICU stay. Additionally, we aim to evaluate whether the partial pressure of arterial oxygen (PaO_2) to the fraction of inspired oxygen (FiO_2) ratio is lower in patients with NOAF treated with amiodarone compared to patients with NOAF treated with digoxin or beta-blockers.

2. Study objectives and purpose

We will conduct a retrospective observational cohort study investigating all Danish patients included in the Handling Oxygenation Targets in the ICU (HOT-ICU) trial (11) and the Handling Oxygenation Targets in COVID-19 (HOT-COVID) trial (12) who developed NOAF within the first 7 days of inclusion in the trials.

We hypothesise that patients with NOAF have a higher mortality rate, fewer days alive without life support and fewer days alive out of hospital at 90 days follow-up compared to patients without NOAF. We also hypothesise that patients treated with amiodarone for NOAF will have a lower $\text{PaO}_2:\text{FiO}_2$ ratio over time from initiation of the treatment and up to a maximum of 14 days compared to those treated with digoxin or beta-blockers for NOAF.

3. Methods and study population

The study will be conducted as a retrospective observational cohort study based on Danish patients included in the HOT-ICU trial (11) and the HOT-COVID trial (12). Baseline data are obtained from the electronic Case Report Forms (eCRF) used in the two studies. Patients with NOAF within the first 7 days after inclusion in the trials will be identified by manually screening of medical records and all information of antiarrhythmic treatment will be collected. All arterial blood gas (ABG) data for all included patients will be obtained from the Radiometer Medical Aps database.

In both trials the inclusion criteria were severe acute hypoxaemic respiratory failure (11, 12), and randomisation was carried out within 12 hours after ICU admission. The number of Danish patients included in the two trials were 2883 patients out of a total of 3625 patients.

Preliminary data from 410 patients included in the HOT-ICU trial at Aalborg University Hospital showed that 26% developed NOAF during the first 7 days in the ICU and that 82% of those patients were treated with amiodarone. The data from the HOT-COVID trial has not yet been evaluated. Of note, digoxin was primarily used for NOAF in the SARS-CoV-2 patients at Aalborg University Hospital, due to concerns about acute APT. Therefore, it is assumed that the number of patients with NOAF treated with amiodarone versus digoxin or beta-blockers, will be of sufficient size to enable a comparison of differences in PaO₂:FiO₂ ratio between the two groups.

Inclusion criteria:

- Included in the HOT-ICU or the HOT-COVID trials in Denmark
- Development of NOAF within 7 days after ICU admission
- Treatment with amiodarone, digoxin, or beta-blockers

Definition and diagnosis of NOAF according to guidelines from the Danish Society of Anesthesiology and Intensive Care Medicine (3).

Exclusion criteria:

- Withdrawn informed consent for the use of data in the HOT-ICU and HOT-COVID trials
- Permanent or persistent AF prior to the ICU admission
- Paroxysmal atrial fibrillation treated with anti-arrhythmia agents prior to the ICU admission
- Development of NOAF more than 7 days after ICU admission
- Development of NOAF within hospitalisation, but prior to ICU admission
- Development of NOAF within 7 days after ICU admission, but no medical treatment for NOAF in the ICU

4. Data Collection Methods

Patients from the HOT-ICU and HOT-COVID trial databases, included at sites in Denmark, will undergo systematic screening for NOAF during the ICU stay from time of inclusion in the studies and up to 7 days thereafter. If patients are found eligible for inclusion in the current study, data will be recorded from start of administration of amiodarone, digoxin or beta-blockers and up to a maximum of 14 days.

Patients included at sites located in Jutland, will be identified through manually screening of medical records. Patients included in Capital Region and Region Zealand will be identified using a programmed screening tool in 'Sundhedsplatformen' to capture those who were treated with amiodarone, digoxin or beta-blockers during their ICU stay. The initial electronic screening will thereafter be followed by manually screening of medical records.

Baseline variables are obtained from eCRFs of the HOT-ICU (11) and HOT-COVID (12) trials. In the eCRFs, only the highest and lowest value of PaO₂ with concomitant FiO₂s were registered every 12 hours. To obtain a more comprehensive dataset, all ABG data (average 6 ABGs per patient per day in the ICU) were obtained (Radiometer Medical Aps database). Data describing the treatment of NOAF are obtained from the medical records. In the context of data collection, a day in the ICU is defined as from 06:00 hour to 05:59 hour the next morning.

Baseline variables from eCRFs

- Date and time of ICU admission
- Age
- Gender
- Chronic illness
- Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA) score
- Type of ICU admission
- Acute illness
- Respiratory support at baseline (mechanical invasive ventilation, non-invasive ventilation, continuous positive airway pressure or oxygen in open systems)

Daily registered variables from eCRFs

- Mechanical ventilation, specified as invasive or non-invasive mechanical ventilation, or non-intermittent CPAP
- Use of vasopressors or inotropes
- Use of renal replacement therapy

Variables obtained from medical records in patients with NOAF:

- Date of NOAF
- Daily treatment of NOAF (i.e., amiodarone, beta-blockers, digoxin, synchronized cardioversion) yes/no
- If treated with amiodarone
 - Total daily intravenous bolus dosage
 - Total daily continuous intravenous dosage
 - Total daily oral dosage
- If treated with digoxin:
 - Total daily dosage
- If treated with beta-blockers:
 - Total daily dosage
- If treated with other agents:
 - Total daily dosage

Data will be registered from onset of NOAF and until treatment is discontinued up to a maximum of 14 days after first treatment. If treatment is paused, but resumed during the observational period, data for the intervening period is also recorded.

ABG data

- PaO₂
- FiO₂

5. Data management plan

All data will be managed using REDCap[®] hosted at North Denmark Region. The HOT-ICU trial and HOT-COVID data is stored in OpenClinica[®] software (OpenClinica, LLC, Waltham, MA 02451, USA). All statistical analyses will be conducted using Stata version 18, STATA Nordic.

6. Outcome measures

Co-Primary:

- 90-day all-cause mortality*
- Days alive without life support in 90 days (life support is defined as mechanical ventilation, renal replacement therapy, or vasopressor or inotrope infusion)*

Secondary:

- 1-year all-cause mortality*

- Days alive out of hospital at 90 days follow-up*
- Changes in PaO₂:FiO₂ ratio from initiation of antiarrhythmic treatment and up to a maximum of 14 days in patients treated with amiodarone compared to patients treated with digoxin or beta-blockers.

*after randomisation in the HOT-ICU and the HOT-COVID trials

7. Data analysis plan

As this is a subgroup analysis, we do not conduct a sample size estimation. All Danish patients from the HOT-ICU and HOT-COVID trials who provided consent will be included in the analysis.

We will compare patients who developed NOAF within the first 7 days after randomisation with patients in the remaining cohort that did not develop NOAF during their ICU stay.

The data will be analyzed using mixed effect generalized linear models (MEGLM), incorporating robust variance estimation and a hierarchical variance model by trial site and patients. We will use a random intercept model by patients when achieving no estimation convergence.

We will analyze the 90-day mortality using a Poisson error distribution with a log link to produce relative risks (RR) and an identity link for risk differences (RD). We will adjust for the presence or absence of active hematological malignancy, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, and the oxygenation target.

In a secondary analysis, we will make additional adjustments for the baseline variables age, presence or absence of active metastatic cancer, admission type, and SOFA score. We will also report mortality using Kaplan-Meier plots. We will analyse the number of days alive without life support and days alive out of hospital at 90 days using a Poisson error distribution and a log link.

We will estimate the daily time-weighted averages for the PaO₂:FiO₂ ratio and amiodarone accumulated doses from the initiation of antiarrhythmic treatment up to a maximum of 14 days. The time-weighted averages will be analyzed using a Gaussian error distribution with an identity link.

We will report results with 95% confidence intervals (CIs). P-values less than 0.05 will be considered statistically significant. We will handle missing values using mixed regression. We will conduct all analyses using Stata Statistical Software, Release 18 (StataCorp LLC, College Station, TX, 2023).

8. Ethical considerations

The HOT-ICU trial was approved by the Committee on Health Research Ethics in the North Denmark Region (N-20170015), and the Danish Data Protection Agency (2008-58-0028). The HOT-COVID trial was approved as an amendment to the HOT-ICU trial in August 2020. The approvals end on 31 December 2024.

9. Plan for publication, authorship and dissemination

The study is initiated by Prof. Bodil Steen Rasmussen. Results, whether positive, negative, or inconclusive, will be published in a relevant peer-reviewed journal. Each site contributing to data collection

will be granted co-authorship. The results will be presented at scientific conferences and meetings. The study results will also be communicated to the health care professionals and to the public in Denmark.

10. Timeline

Data collection was initiated on 1 June 2024 and should be completed no later than on 31 December 2024. Data will be analysed in February 2025, and the manuscript will be prepared in the spring of 2025.

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